

Tohono O'odham Facts, History, and Culture

**A conversation with Jacelle Ramon-Sauberan
by Katy Garmany (NOIRLab)**

As part of our effort to develop informational materials for the professional community and the public about the Tohono O'odham Nation, where Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) is located, NOIRLab has been working with Jacelle Ramon-Sauberan. Jacelle is a PhD candidate in the University of Arizona American Indian Studies Program and a member of the Tohono O'odham Nation. The following is an informal interview with Jacelle, conducted by Katy Garmany of NOIRLab.

Katy: Let's start with a few quick facts: How many people live on the Tohono O'odham Nation? How big is it? How many traffic lights are there? Can non-O'odham live there?

Jacelle: There are about 34,000 enrolled tribal members, with half living on the reservation and half off the reservation. There are no traffic lights on my reservation, just stop signs. Traditionally, if an O'odham married a non-O'odham, they would live off the reservation. But that has changed over time, and there are non-O'odham living on the reservation.

The Tohono O'odham Reservation is 2.8 million acres and is broken up into four parcels. The four parcels are San Xavier; Main (where KPNO resides); San Lucy District near Gila Bend, Arizona; and Florence Village near Florence, Arizona. The Main part of the reservation is approximately the size of the state of Connecticut with one grocery store

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and one post office. For some tribal members, it can take 2–3 hours one way to check their mail, purchase food, or buy gas/fuel.

Katy: Some people remember when you were referred to as the Papagos. Can you explain the history of this name and why your Nation changed it?

Jacelle: The name Papago was given to us by the Spanish, and there are different stories on how we got the name, but the bottom line is that it was a lack of understanding / language barrier. Papago translates to “Bean Eater,” because one of our traditional foods is tepary beans. In 1986, my tribe changed our name to what we call ourselves, which is Tohono O'odham. Tohono means Desert and O'odham means People. So if you ever write or talk about O'odham, do not say O'odham people because you are saying “People people.”

Katy: The Nation has its own language. How has this been preserved? Do younger people speak it fluently?

Jacelle: The O'odham language is still spoken. However, it was put on the endangered language list by UNESCO. There are O'odham-language classes offered at the University of Arizona and Tohono O'odham Community College. Also, there are O'odham-language teachers within the pre-K through 12th grade schools on our reservations. Our

language is mostly spoken by older people, and there are not nearly enough youth who speak it fluently.

Katy: The TON borders Mexico. How do border issues affect daily life for the Nation?

Jacelle: You cannot leave my reservation without going through a Border Patrol checkpoint. More recently, the border wall has affected my tribe by the desecration of sacred areas where our ancestors are buried and where we have a spring called Quitobaquito. Also, in the construction of the wall, saguaro cacti (Ha:san/Haha:san) have been bulldozed. We view saguaros as human beings, so seeing them being hurt is not okay.

Katy: How does government work on the Nation? Is the TON a sovereign nation?

Jacelle: The Tohono O'odham Nation is comprised of three branches of government: Executive (which houses the Chairman and Vice Chairman of the Nation), Legislative (which houses the Tribal Council representatives: 2 from each of the 11 Districts), and Judicial (which houses the courts and judges). The Tohono O'odham Nation is divided into 11 Districts, and each District has its own chairman and vice chairman. The 11 Districts are Baboquivari, Chukut Kuk, Gu Achi, Gu Vo, Hickiwan, Pisinemo, San Lucy, San Xavier, Schuk Toak, Sells, and Sif Oidak.

To better understand: Look at the Tohono O'odham Nation as if it were the United States. The Districts are like states, and within the Districts, there are communities that would be like towns. And our Chairman is like a President, and the District Chairman would be like a governor, and the Legislative Representatives are like State Representatives.

Katy: Most people have very little knowledge of the history and culture of the Tohono O'odham even if they live in Tucson! What are some of the things you find yourself explaining over and over to people you meet?

Jacelle: How to pronounce Tohono O'odham. If the person can't get the pronunciation down, I tell them it is okay to just say "T.O."

Katy: Astronomers, of course, know Kitt Peak National Observatory is on your Nation. How do you think most O'odham view the observatory?

Jacelle: I cannot speak for others, but for myself I have never had any issues with the observatory being on the O'odham *jewed* (land). It was something agreed upon between O'odham and astronomers. The old photos I have seen from the lease signing and when O'odham took astronomers on horseback to the top of Ioligam Du'ag (Kitt Peak Mountain) are amazing and historical.

Katy: What sorts of things can NOIRLab, which operates Kitt Peak National Observatory, do to be a better neighbor?

Jacelle: I just ask that NOIRLab continue working on building a relationship with my Tribe, especially the Schuk Toak District where the observatory resides.

Katy: If someone wants to visit Sells, what should they know in order to be respectful?

Jacelle: O'odham have been here for time immemorial, and we view the O'odham *jewed* as the center of the Earth. So if you visit our reservation, understand you are visitors. Please respect our culture, traditions, and way of life. I guess it would be similar thinking to if you visited another country.

Jacelle Ramon-Sauberan is Tohono O'odham and from the San Xavier District. A PhD candidate in American Indian Studies with a minor in journalism, Jacelle's dissertation topic is on the history of land and water in San Xavier. She is also an adjunct instructor at Tohono O'odham Community College, where she teaches Tohono O'odham history and culture. A two-time graduate of the American Indian Journalism Institute, as well as the Chips Quinn Scholars Program for Diversity in Journalism and The New York Times Student Journalism Institute, Jacelle has written for news publications in Arizona, New Mexico, Washington, South Dakota, Oklahoma, Tennessee, Florida, and New York. She was also a freelance journalist for the Indian Country Today Media Network from 2009 to 2017.

To learn more, visit the Tohono O'odham Nation's website
(<http://www.tonation-nsn.gov>)
and that of their cultural museum
(<http://www.himdagki.org>).